

CLASSIFICATION AND DETECTION OF *Plasmodium Vivax* INFECTED CELLS IN BLOOD SMEARS IMAGES

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INTRODUCTION

In Guatemala, this type of diagnosis (*P. Vivax malaria*) has several disadvantages, trained and experienced microscopist personnel are needed to identify and quantify the parasite in the thick drop (gold standard) and blood smears. There is also a high workload for the staff on the area in which the disease is concentrated; high estimated time in observation of blood films, on average a trained person observes a thick blood film for 10 to 20 minutes, in endemic areas a health center can receive between 200 and 300 weekly blood films, producing ocular fatigue, which is usually the most influential factor in an incorrect diagnosis. Automation test through CNN networks it could accelerate diagnoses, increase the efficiency and performance of specialists.

We used image set *P. Vivax(malaria)* infected human blood smears, accession number BBBC041version 1, available from the Broad Bioimage Benchmark Collection (Ljosa et al., 2012). The images in the dataset contains 1,364 images, with a total of 80,113 labeled cells, different researchers contributed labeling each cell in the dataset. These images were contributed by Jane Hung of MIT and the Broad Institute in Cambridge, MA. Each cell in the biological images has a class label and the bounding box coordinates, for the infected cell he have four classes gametocytes, rings, trophozoites and schizonts

METHODOLOGY

To increase the training data and remove the imbalance of the dataset for one of the classes and improve the generalization ability of the models, we first cropped all parasites from images using the bounding box location and augmented these images with rotations, then we generated a method that randomly adds parasites into the training images that had less than four parasites, the method always add the parasite class that has fewer occurrences this runs until the different classes are close to be balanced.

Percentage of parasites in data

RESULTS

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Model	IoU	Precision	Recall	F1 Score
U-Net	71.1%	27.81%	44.29%	34.16%
YOLO	77.17%	45.41%	3.77%	6.96%
YOLO 1st augmented dataset	77.19%	41.56%	4.08%	7.44%
YOLO 2nd augmented dataset	84.85%	57.26%	5.13%	9.42%
YOLO 3rd augmented dataset	83.66%	46.71%	7.16%	12.42%

CONCLUSION

We were able to detect malaria parasites in the images, training the models with augmented datasets helped to improve the performance. In the future, we plan to extend this work, gathering our dataset, will be an important step, also creating an ensemble prediction using both models; we will also experiment with different novel models. Once we reach better performance measures we plan to automate the whole process using a robotic arm for manipulating the blood samples, the goal is to automate the complete process.

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Original data available from the Broad Institute Repository at <https://data.broadinstitute.org/bbbc/BBBC041/>

These images were contributed by Jane Hung of MIT and the Broad Institute in Cambridge, MA.

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Original Data Set

Augmented Data Set 1

Augmented Data Set 2

